

Government Sector Performance of Pakistan, South Asia and 34 OED Countries – International Policy Issues in the Contemporary World

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Abstract *The paper focuses on the various aspects especially as globally accepted fact is that social and key economic indicators are influenced by the government activities. Public Sector Performance and efficiency reflect government priorities. The paper evaluates the public sector performance of Pakistan by calculating the Public Sector Performance Index based on seven indicators and these seven indicators are further classified into two broad groups. Many international studies have carried out the performance evaluation of public sectors of industrialized countries missing the public sector performance of Pakistan with other countries. With the aim, Public Sector Performance of Pakistan was compared with countries of South Asia and some developed countries. The research analyzes the public sector performance indicators of countries to calculate the overall performance. The paper aims to compare public sector performance of Pakistan with South Asian Countries and members of Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which currently includes 34 Countries.*

Key Words:

Performance Indicator, Public Sector, Performance Evaluation, OECD, Pakistan

Introduction

Public sector performance determines the outcome of activities in Public sector while public sector efficiency is calculated by comparing the finances used as public expenditure in achieving it (Fraser Alert, March 2007). Many studies have been carried out to determine and empirically assess the Public sector performance of countries but have mainly focused the industrialized countries. Over the years, Chinese government have been evaluating the impact of various systems

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implemented in their country and have transitioned from one to another in an effort to improve the evaluation system of public sector performance (Sarfraz, 2014).

Evaluation of Implemented systems by Chinese Government

In an effort to bring transition in China, Chinese government carried out performance evaluation of various levels of government departments. The aim and objective of the activity was to bring transition in the country from a planned economy to market economy. It seems significantly considered because the indicators related to performance also depend on their accessibility and utility in the contextual paradigms (Carter, 2002). In 1990s, performance evaluation systems at various first levels of government, functional departments, social organizations and public level organizations were studied. It was found that some evaluation systems had local characteristics (Zhuhai, 1999).

Evaluation of Internationally Recognized Performance Evaluation Systems by Chinese Government

The performance evaluation systems that were studied also varied in characteristics as regards to contents and methods. Variations were also observed on defining the criteria for evaluation based on cycles or duration and the value. Internationally, there is a consensus that the methods for performance evaluation be based on efficiency, economy and effect. A new concept has included quality as the fourth dimension worth evaluating. Out of all internationally available or adopted performance evaluation systems, “Balance Scorecard” and “3E” are the most widely used performance evaluation system for local government in China (Sarfraz, 2006).

Suitability of Internationally Recognized Systems for China

The existing performance evaluation systems in the world are designed and developed according to the environment and local conditions of the particular area. Applying the same systems across China do not cater for their needs. This either involves changing the values or local systems or requires redefinition of international systems as per the requirements of Chinese local Government keeping in view the local norms, customs and values.

International Studies on Public Sector Performance Evaluation

It is difficult to determine performance of a public organization due to difficulties in defining performance which may be the outcomes coming up on unintentional bases (Smith, 1995). This is a result of problems in defining a meaning of the concept of performance; means of obtaining performance and evaluation of

performance. It also seemingly shows that the performance related indicators may be clearly shown as a set of aspects to be observed and analyzed (Brignall, 2000). They believe that measurement of public sector performance involves taking into account the difference between input, procedures and processes, and the final outcomes (Tanzi, 2000).

Previous studies on efficiency of public sector show the comparison of the PSP factors was determined based on almost seven factors as shown in Figure 1 (Afonso et al 2005).

In March 2007, Fraser Institute carried out a study on comparing performance related to public sector at international level. The study determined the Public Sector Performance and Efficiency of twenty three industrial oriented countries. The performance related to Public Sector was determined on the seven indicators proposed by researchers. The study aimed at evaluating, on the same frame work as done by Fraser Institute, the Public Sector Performance of Pakistan as compared to South Asia and current 34 countries of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (March, 2007).

Public sector performance indicators may base on the goals and objectives of the organizations, relying on to some extent the relative demand of such indicators in the public sector performance measurement (Rainey, 1976). In this way, comparison of the indicators of one Govt. with other Govt. may be a tough job, as it's based on the circumstances, ideologies, and relevancy related aspect, but important issue is to measure and assess in comparison with each other (Walle, 2009). Similarly, comparing based on perceived performance and the actual performance is another issue which may need attention, generating an idea for the system of assessment in organizations (Leeuw, 2002).

Another aspect is the dynamics of performance indicators – here the perspectives related to performance vary as individual perspective, group perspective, team and organizational perspective, but then comes the system perspective of organizational performance which may matters a lot (Fowler, 2000). Researchers and authors also worked a lot on performance management or organizations especially in public sector organizations, where the indicators or markers of performance are considered of great significance (De Bruijn, 2003).

The study calculates the Public Sector Performance Index based on seven indicators. These seven indicators are further classified into two broad groups. The opportunity indicators consisting of administration, education related, health related and public infrastructure results. The “Musgravian” markers and factors include the income distribution, economic stability and Economic Performance. The average of all sub-indicators is the public sector performance indicator

For measuring the performance related to Public Sector in Pakistan, the general form of the score function used is based on the researchers’ proposition and already conducted studies as of Afonso et al, where they proposed various indicators related to this (Schuknecht, 1997).

$$f(x) = \alpha_1 * X_1 + \alpha_2 * X_2 + \alpha_3 * X_3 + \alpha_4 * X_4 + \alpha_5 * X_5 + \alpha_6 * X_6 + \alpha_7 * X_7 ,$$

where:

α_i = the coefficient related to importance

X_i = markers related to performance of public sector

The value of importance related coefficient has been taken as 1 for all the indicators. Each marker contributes one seventh towards the resultant performance of public sector Index provided by the function. X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 are opportunity indicators as named by Afonso, Schuknecht and Tanzi, while X_5 , X_6 and X_7 are the Musgravian Indicators named after Harvard Professor Richard A. Musgrave (Fraser et al. 2007).

Each indicator is composed of equally contributing sub indicators. The details of sub indicators for each indicator are as follows

X_1 = *Administrative*: Composed of 4 sub-indicators:

- (a) Corruption
- (b) Red tape
- (c) Quality of Judiciary
- (d) Shadow Economy

X_2 = *Education*: Consisting of 2 sub-indicators:

- (a) Secondary School Enrolment
- (b) Education Achievement

X_3 = *Health*: Consisting of 2 sub-indicators:

- (a) Infant Mortality
- (b) Life Expectancy

X_4 = *Public Infrastructure*: Having one sub-indicator - quality communication and transport infrastructure

X_5 = *Distribution*: Which is calculated on Inequality of Income Distribution

X_6 = *Stability*: Gives equal weights to 2 sub-indicators:

- (a) Stability of GDP growth
- (b) Inflation

X_7 = *Economic performance*: Determined on 3 sub-indicators

- (a) GDP per capita (PPP)
- (b) GDP growth
- (c) Unemployment for the last 10 years

Instrumentation

Figure 1. Total Public Sector Performance (PSP) Indicator

Source: Afonso, Schuknecht, and Tanzi, 2005

Population and Sample

For the purpose of research, the Public Sector Performance of Pakistan was compared with countries of South Asia and some developed countries. The South Asian Countries include Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal

and Sri Lanka while the 23 OECD countries taken for comparison include Australia, Canada, Japan, United States of America and United Kingdom.

Data Collection Methods

The data was collected from various sources. The detailed source of input data for each sub-indicator to calculate the respective indicator is as follows:

Administrative

This opportunity indicator is composed of 4 sub-indicators:

1. **Corruption:** In order to quantify the indicator of corruption and gauge it, CPI, which is called Corruption Perception Index (CPI) 2014, is employed. This marker is also utilized by many other authentic researchers and organizations including Transparency International as the input.

2. **Red Tape:** To quantifying this sub-indicator, we have used the Ease of Doing Business index defined by World Bank. Ease of doing business ranks economies from 1 to 189, with first place being the best. A high ranking (a low numerical rank) means that the regulatory environment is conducive to business operation. The index averages the country's percentile rankings on 10 topics covered in the World Bank's Doing Business. The ranking on each topic is the simple average of the percentile rankings on its component indicators. In our research, higher value indicates better performance in that indicator. Therefore, the ease of doing business index provided by World Bank had to be reversed by subtracting the value out of 200. The more numerical value indicates the regulatory environment is more conducive to the starting and operation of a local firm. So Canada gained 184 points while Afghanistan received 17 points.

3. **Quality of Judiciary:** This indicator has been calculated from the efficiency of legal framework for private business in settling disputes. The values have been taken from the Global Competitiveness Report 2104-15.

4. **Shadow Economy:** Shadow economy is the informal economy. Also called black market or underground economy, it is a market where transaction of goods or services is done illegally. The goods or services may or may not themselves be illegal to own, or to trade through other, legal channels. This sub-indicator shows the GDP percentage of underground economy and is based on the International reports. The values for shadow economies of the countries under study have been taken from World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No 5356 titled Shadow Economies All over the World from 1999 to 2007 (Montenegro, 2010).

Education

Education consists of 2 sub-indicators

1. **Secondary School Enrolment:** The values for this indicator have been taken from the Secondary School Enrollment rate provided in Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. The data related to Afghanistan and Maldives was not available. The higher the value, the better the country in that indicator

2. **Education Achievement:** To assess this indicator, we have used the Quality of Education System indicates how well does the education system in a country meets the needs of a competitive economy. The values have been taken from the Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. The data related to Afghanistan and Maldives was not available. The higher the value in the indicator, the better the performance of the country.

Health

Health comprises 2 sub-indicators:

1. **Infant Mortality:** This indicator indicates the mortality of infant children (aged 0-12 months) per 1000 live births. The data for this indicator for the year 2013 has been taken from the Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. Due to non-availability of data relating to Afghanistan and Maldives in this report, the data for these countries has been taken from CIA World Fact Book, which provides values for year 2014. In order to standardize with our model of higher value equals better performance, the mortality rate was subtracted from 1000 to determine the number of child surviving per 1000 live births.

2. **Life Expectancy:** The values for this indicator for the year 2013 have been taken from the Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. Due to non-availability of data relating to Afghanistan and Maldives in this report, the data for these countries has been taken from CIA World Fact Book which provides values for year 2014.

3. **Public Infrastructure:** This aspect contains single sub-indicator that is quality communication and transport infrastructure. To check the standardized data, we tried to follow world economic forum, the Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. The data related to Afghanistan and Maldives was not available.

4. **Distribution:** This is determined from the Gini coefficient, named after Corrado Gini an Italian statistician, demographer and sociologist, which measure the degree of inequality in the distribution of family income in a country. A value of 0 represents absolute equality, a value of 100 absolute inequalities. The data for GINI Index has been taken from CIA World Fact Book. In case of Afghanistan,

the values have been taken from UNDP Human Development Report October 2013. In order to standardize with our model of higher value equals better performance, the Inequality control was determined by subtracting the GINI index from 100. The higher the values of Inequality control, better the performance.

Stability

Stability indicator is based on equal weights of the following 2 sub-indicators

1. **Stability of GDP Growth:** This indicator determines the coefficient of variation in the growth of GDP. The data related to this indicator could not be determined.
2. **Inflation:** This is the annual percentage change in the consumer price index. The data for year 2013 was taken from the Global Competitiveness Report 2014-15. The data for year 2013 related to Afghanistan and Maldives has been taken from CIA World Fact Book. In order to standardize with our model of higher value equals better performance, the Inflation Control was determined by the subtracting the inflation from 10. The higher the values of Inflation Control, better the performance.

Economic Performance

It relies on three factors

1. **GDP Per Capita (PPP):** It is the total output of a country and is obtained by dividing the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) with the number of people in the country. An increase in GDP per capita indicates growth in productivity. The 2013 data of GDP in US Dollars was taken from Global Competitiveness Report 2014. Due to non-availability of data regarding Afghanistan and Maldives, their 2014 GDP in US Dollars was taken from CIA World Fact Book which is substantiated by the research field experts (CIA World Fact Book, 2014).
2. **GDP Growth:** It is the annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices on constant local currency. The data for the year 2013 for GDP growth in annual percentage has been taken from the World Bank Report.
3. **Unemployment for the Last 10 Years:** The International Labor Organization (ILO), defines it that unemployed people are the people who have no work but they are actively ready to work and showing their willingness. The yearly data in percentage for 2004-2014 has been taken from World Economic Outlook Database, October 2013. The average of the data was taken for last ten years from 2004-2014. For Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Maldives and Nepal, the data was not available in the abovementioned database, therefore, the yearly values of unemployment given at CIA World Fact Book were taken. To keep the data in line

with the evaluation criteria of better performance with a higher value, the values of unemployment were subtracted from 100 to calculate the employment value which has been used for calculating the score. In this scenario, the reconsideration of fiscal role of govt. is also considered very important.

Analysis

After entering the values for the individual sub indicators, performance of countries was determined for the each indicator contributing towards calculation of Public Sector Performance (PSP) index.

Administrative

The data for the administrative indicator and its analysis is shown in Table 1 given on the next page. The graph (Figure 2) shows that Bhutan stands out administratively among the South Asian countries whereas Pakistan stands fifth after Bhutan, Sri Lanka, India and Nepal.

Figure 2 : Administrative wrt South Asia

A comparison with 34 OECD countries (Figure 3) shows that Pakistan has the lowest score of 0.60 while New Zealand stands out with a score of 1.24.

Table 1.

S. No.	Country	Corruption			Red Tape				Quality of Judiciary			Shadow Economy				Ave · Sco re
		Transparency International			Ease of Doing Business Index (World Bank)				Global Competitiveness Report 2014			Informal Economy				
		Year	CPI	Score	Year	Index	How Easy	Score	Year	Index	Score	Year	Index	How much controlled	Score	
Pakistan with respect to South Asian Countries																
1	Afghanistan	2014	12	0.37	2014	183	17	0.26	2014	0	0.00	Average of 1000-2007	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16
2	Bangladesh	2014	25	0.77	2014	173	27	0.41	2014	2.9	1.07		35.30	64.70	1.11	0.84
3	Bhutan	2014	65	1.99	2014	125	75	1.14	2014	4.1	1.52		28.70	71.30	1.22	1.47
4	India	2014	38	1.16	2014	142	58	0.88	2014	3.8	1.41		22.20	77.80	1.33	1.20
5	Maldives	2014	25	0.77	2014	116	84	1.28	2014	0	0.00		29.50	70.50	1.21	0.81
6	Nepal	2014	29	0.89	2014	108	92	1.40	2014	2.9	1.07		36.70	63.30	1.08	1.11
7	Pakistan	2014	29	0.89	2014	128	72	1.10	2014	3.3	1.22		35.70	64.30	1.10	1.08
8	Sri Lanka	2014	38	1.16	2014	99	101	1.54	2014	4.6	1.70		43.90	56.10	0.96	1.34
	Total		261	8.00		1074	526	8.00		21.6	8.00		232.00	468.00	8.00	8.00
	Average		32.63	1.00		134.25	65.75	1.00		2.70	1.00		29.00	58.50	1.00	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries																
1	Pakistan	2014	29	0.43	2014	128	72	0.42	2014	3.3	0.76	Average of 1999-2007	35.7	64.30	0.80	0.60
2	Australia	2014	80	1.17	2014	10	190	1.12	2014	4.8	1.11		14.0	86.00	1.07	1.12
3	Austria	2014	72	1.06	2014	21	179	1.05	2014	4.9	1.13		9.7	90.30	1.12	1.09
4	Belgium	2014	76	1.12	2014	42	158	0.93	2014	4.2	0.97		21.9	78.10	0.97	1.00
5	Canada	2014	81	1.19	2014	16	184	1.08	2014	5.5	1.27		15.7	84.30	1.05	1.15
6	Chile	2014	73	1.07	2014	41	159	0.94	2014	4.4	1.02		19.3	80.70	1.00	1.01
7	Czech Republic	2014	51	0.75	2014	44	156	0.92	2014	3.3	0.76		18.4	81.60	1.01	0.86
8	Denmark	2014	92	1.35	2014	4	196	1.15	2014	5.0	1.16		17.7	82.30	1.02	1.17

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9	Estonia	2014	69	1.01	2014	17	183	1.08	2014	4.3	0.99		31.2	68.80	0.85	0.99
10	Finland	2014	89	1.31	2014	9	191	1.13	2014	6.0	1.39		17.7	82.30	1.02	1.21
11	France	2014	69	1.01	2014	31	169	1.00	2014	4.2	0.97		15.0	85.00	1.06	1.01
12	Germany	2014	79	1.16	2014	14	186	1.10	2014	5.4	1.25		16.0	84.00	1.04	1.14
13	Greece	2014	43	0.63	2014	61	139	0.82	2014	2.7	0.62		27.5	72.50	0.90	0.74
14	Hungary	2014	54	0.79	2014	54	146	0.86	2014	3.3	0.76		24.4	75.60	0.94	0.84
15	Iceland	2014	79	1.16	2014	12	188	1.11	2014	4.9	1.13		15.6	84.40	1.05	1.11
16	Ireland	2014	74	1.09	2014	13	187	1.10	2014	4.9	1.13		15.8	84.20	1.05	1.09
17	Israel	2014	60	0.88	2014	40	160	0.94	2014	4.1	0.95		22.0	78.00	0.97	0.94
18	Italy	2014	43	0.63	2014	56	144	0.85	2014	2.0	0.46		27.0	73.00	0.91	0.71
19	Japan	2014	76	1.12	2014	29	171	1.01	2014	5.2	1.20		11.0	89.00	1.11	1.11
20	South Korea	2014	55	0.81	2014	5	195	1.15	2014	3.5	0.81		26.8	73.20	0.91	0.92
21	Luxembourg	2014	82	1.20	2014	59	141	0.83	2014	5.4	1.25		9.7	90.30	1.12	1.10
22	Mexico	2014	35	0.51	2014	39	161	0.95	2014	3.3	0.76		30.0	70.00	0.87	0.77
23	Netherlands	2014	83	1.22	2014	27	173	1.02	2014	5.5	1.27		13.2	86.80	1.08	1.15
24	New Zealand	2014	91	1.34	2014	2	198	1.17	2014	5.9	1.36		12.4	87.60	1.09	1.24
25	Norway	2014	86	1.26	2014	6	194	1.14	2014	5.6	1.29		18.7	81.30	1.01	1.18
26	Poland	2014	61	0.90	2014	32	168	0.99	2014	2.9	0.67		27.2	72.80	0.90	0.87
27	Portugal	2014	63	0.93	2014	25	175	1.03	2014	3.1	0.72		23.0	77.00	0.96	0.91
28	Slovakia	2014	50	0.73	2014	37	163	0.96	2014	2.4	0.55		18.1	81.90	1.02	0.82
29	Slovenia	2014	58	0.85	2014	51	149	0.88	2014	2.6	0.60		26.2	73.80	0.92	0.81
30	Spain	2014	60	0.88	2014	33	167	0.98	2014	3.4	0.79		22.5	77.50	0.96	0.90
31	Sweden	2014	87	1.28	2014	11	189	1.11	2014	5.4	1.25		18.8	81.20	1.01	1.16
32	Switzerland	2014	86	1.26	2014	20	180	1.06	2014	5.6	1.29		8.5	91.50	1.14	1.19
33	Turkey	2014	45	0.66	2014	55	145	0.85	2014	3.8	0.88		31.3	68.70	0.85	0.81
34	United Kingdom	2014	78	1.15	2014	8	192	1.13	2014	5.7	1.32		12.5	87.50	1.09	1.17
35	United States	2014	74	1.09	2014	7	193	1.14	2014	4.9	1.13		8.6	91.40	1.14	1.12
	Total		2383.0	35.0		1059.0	5941.0	35.0		151.40	35.0		683.1	2816.9	35.0	35.0
	Average		68.09	1.00		30.26	169.74	1.00		4.33	1.00		19.52	80.48	1.00	1.00

Figure 3 : Administrative with respect to OECD Countries

Education

The analysis of data for the Education sub-indicator analysis is shown in Table 2 given on the next page. Due to non-availability of data regarding Afghanistan and Maldives, their scores could not be calculated. The graph (Figure 4) shows Sri Lanka leading in Education with a score of 1.79 while Pakistan stands lowest.

Figure 4 : Education with respect to South Asia

Table 2. Education

S No	Country	Secondary Education Enrollment Rate			Education Achievement			Average Score
		Global Competitiveness Report 2014			Global Competitiveness Report 2014			
		Year	Rate	Score	Year	Average Index	Score	
Pakistan with respect to South Asia								
1	Afghanistan	2013	0	0.00	2013-14	0	0.00	0.00
2	Bangladesh	2013	53.6	1.08	2013-14	3.3	1.14	1.11
3	Bhutan	2013	73.9	1.48	2013-14	4	1.39	1.43
4	India	2013	68.5	1.38	2013-14	4.2	1.45	1.41
5	Maldives	2013	0	0.00	2013-14	0	0.00	0.00
6	Nepal	2013	66.6	1.34	2013-14	3.6	1.25	1.29
7	Pakistan	2013	36.6	0.73	2013-14	3.4	1.18	0.96
8	Sri Lanka	2013	99.3	1.99	2013-14	4.6	1.59	1.79
	Total		398.5	8		23.1	8	8
	Average		49.81	1.00		2.89	1.00	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries								
1	Pakistan	2013	36.6	0.36	2013-14	3.4	0.78	0.57
2	Australia	2013	135.5	1.32	2013-14	4.8	1.11	1.21
3	Austria	2013	97.7	0.95	2013-14	4.5	1.04	0.99
4	Belgium	2013	107.3	1.04	2013-14	5.3	1.22	1.13
5	Canada	2013	103.4	1.00	2013-14	5.2	1.20	1.10
6	Chile	2013	89	0.86	2013-14	3.7	0.85	0.86
7	Czech Republic	2013	96.6	0.94	2013-14	3.6	0.83	0.88
8	Denmark	2013	124.7	1.21	2013-14	4.8	1.11	1.16
9	Estonia	2013	107.1	1.04	2013-14	4.4	1.02	1.03
10	Finland	2013	107.7	1.05	2013-14	5.9	1.36	1.20

11	France	2013	109.7	1.06	2013-14	4.4	1.02	1.04
12	Germany	2013	101.3	0.98	2013-14	5.2	1.20	1.09
13	Greece	2013	107.9	1.05	2013-14	3	0.69	0.87
14	Hungary	2013	101.6	0.99	2013-14	3.3	0.76	0.87
15	Iceland	2013	108.6	1.05	2013-14	4.9	1.13	1.09
16	Ireland	2013	119.1	1.16	2013-14	5.4	1.25	1.20
17	Israel	2013	101.7	0.99	2013-14	3.7	0.85	0.92
18	Italy	2013	100.7	0.98	2013-14	3.7	0.85	0.92
19	Japan	2013	101.8	0.99	2013-14	4.4	1.02	1.00
20	South Korea	2013	97.2	0.94	2013-14	3.6	0.83	0.89
21	Luxembourg	2013	101	0.98	2013-14	4.6	1.06	1.02
22	Mexico	2013	85.7	0.83	2013-14	2.8	0.65	0.74
23	Netherlands	2013	129.9	1.26	2013-14	5.3	1.22	1.24
24	New Zealand	2013	119.5	1.16	2013-14	5.3	1.22	1.19
25	Norway	2013	111.1	1.08	2013-14	5	1.15	1.12
26	Poland	2013	97.7	0.95	2013-14	3.6	0.83	0.89
27	Portugal	2013	112.9	1.10	2013-14	4.3	0.99	1.04
28	Slovakia	2013	93.9	0.91	2013-14	2.8	0.65	0.78
29	Slovenia	2013	97.6	0.95	2013-14	4.1	0.95	0.95
30	Spain	2013	130.8	1.27	2013-14	3.4	0.78	1.03
31	Sweden	2013	98.4	0.96	2013-14	4.6	1.06	1.01
32	Switzerland	2013	96.3	0.93	2013-14	6	1.39	1.16
33	Turkey	2013	86.1	0.84	2013-14	3.4	0.78	0.81
34	United Kingdom	2013	95.4	0.93	2013-14	4.6	1.06	0.99
35	United States	2013	93.7	0.91	2013-14	4.6	1.06	0.99
	Total		3605.20	35.00		151.60	35.00	35.00
	Average		103.01	1.00		4.33	1.00	1.00

Performance comparison of Pakistan with 34 OECD countries in field of education (Figure 5) shows that Pakistan has the lowest score of 0.60 while Netherlands stands out with a score of 1.24.

Figure 5 : Education with respect to OECD Countries

Health

The graph (Figure 6) shows comparison of health indicator which comprises of life expectancy and infant mortality. The data is tabulated in table 3 given on the next page. In health, Pakistan stands second last with a score of 0.98 after Afghanistan with a score of 0.84. High infant mortality rate and low life expectancy are the major contributors for low performance. Sri lanka and Maldives take the top positions with a score of 1.07.

Figure 6: Health with respect to South Asia

Table 3. Health

S No	Country	Life Expectancy			Infant Mortality				Average Score
		Global Competitiveness Report 2014 and CIA World fact Book			Global Competitiveness Report 2014 and CIA World fact Book				
		Year	Years	Score	Year	Per 1000 Births	Survival Per 1000	Score	
Pakistan with respect to South Asia									
1	Afghanistan	2014	50.49	0.75	2014	117.23	882.77	0.93	0.84
2	Bangladesh	2013	70.3	1.04	2013	33.10	966.90	1.01	1.03
3	Bhutan	2013	67.9	1.01	2013	35.70	964.30	1.01	1.01
4	India	2013	66.2	0.98	2013	43.80	956.20	1.00	0.99
5	Maldives	2014	75.15	1.12	2014	24.59	975.41	1.02	1.07
6	Nepal	2013	68	1.01	2013	33.60	966.40	1.01	1.01
7	Pakistan	2013	66.4	0.99	2013	69.30	930.70	0.98	0.98
8	Sri Lanka	2013	74.1	1.10	2013	8.30	991.70	1.04	1.07
	Total		538.54	8		365.62	7634.38	8	8
	Average		67.32	1.00		60.94	954.30	1.00	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries									
	Pakistan	2013	66.4	0.83	2013	69.30	930.70	0.94	0.88
1	Australia	2013	82.1	1.03	2013	4.10	995.90	1.00	1.01
2	Austria	2013	80.9	1.01	2013	3.30	996.70	1.00	1.01
3	Belgium	2013	80.4	1.01	2013	3.40	996.60	1.00	1.00
4	Canada	2013	81.2	1.02	2013	4.70	995.30	1.00	1.01
5	Chile	2013	79.6	1.00	2013	7.80	992.20	1.00	1.00
6	Czech Republic	2013	78.10	0.98	2013	3.10	996.90	1.00	0.99
7	Denmark	2013	80.10	1.00	2013	3.00	997.00	1.00	1.00
8	Estonia	2013	76.40	0.96	2013	2.90	997.10	1.00	0.98

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9	Finland	2013	80.60	1.01	2013	2.40	997.60	1.00	1.01
10	France	2013	82.60	1.03	2013	3.40	996.60	1.00	1.02
11	Germany	2013	80.90	1.01	2013	3.40	996.60	1.00	1.01
12	Greece	2013	80.60	1.01	2013	4.10	995.90	1.00	1.01
13	Hungary	2013	75.10	0.94	2013	5.30	994.70	1.00	0.97
14	Iceland	2013	82.90	1.04	2013	1.80	998.20	1.00	1.02
15	Ireland	2013	80.90	1.01	2013	3.40	996.60	1.00	1.01
16	Israel	2013	81.70	1.02	2013	3.30	996.70	1.00	1.01
17	Italy	2013	82.90	1.04	2013	3.20	996.80	1.00	1.02
18	Japan	2013	83.10	1.04	2013	2.20	997.80	1.00	1.02
19	South Korea	2013	81.40	1.02	2013	3.30	996.70	1.00	1.01
20	Luxembourg	2013	81.40	1.02	2013	1.70	998.30	1.00	1.01
21	Mexico	2013	77.10	0.97	2013	13.90	986.10	0.99	0.98
22	Netherlands	2013	81.10	1.02	2013	3.40	996.60	1.00	1.01
23	New Zealand	2013	81.20	1.02	2013	4.70	995.30	1.00	1.01
24	Norway	2013	81.50	1.02	2013	2.20	997.80	1.00	1.01
25	Poland	2013	76.80	0.96	2013	4.30	995.70	1.00	0.98
26	Portugal	2013	80.4	1.01	2013	2.9	997.10	1.00	1.00
27	Slovakia	2013	76.1	0.95	2013	6.3	993.70	1.00	0.98
28	Slovenia	2013	80.1	1.00	2013	2.5	997.50	1.00	1.00
29	Spain	2013	82.4	1.03	2013	3.8	996.20	1.00	1.02
30	Sweden	2013	81.7	1.02	2013	2.3	997.70	1.00	1.01
31	Switzerland	2013	82.7	1.04	2013	3.7	996.30	1.00	1.02
32	Turkey	2013	74.9	0.94	2013	12.2	987.80	0.99	0.97
33	United Kingdom	2013	81.5	1.02	2013	4.1	995.90	1.00	1.01
34	United States	2013	78.7	0.99	2013	6	994.00	1.00	0.99
	Total		2795.5	35			34788.6	35	35
	Average		79.87	1.00			993.96	1.00	1.00

When compared with 34 OECD countries (Figure 7), Pakistan is lowest with a score of 0.88 while Japan leading with as score of 1.02214 followed by Iceland.

Figure 7 : Health with respect to OECD Countries

Infrastructure

The graph (Figure 8) shows comparison of Infrastructure indicator which indicates the quality of communication and transport infrastructure of a country. The data analysis is tabulated in table 4 given on the next page. Data related to Afghanistan and Maldives was not available. With regards to infrastructure, Pakistan stands fourth with a score of 1.18 while the list in South Asia is topped by Sri Lanka with a score of 1.79.

Figure 8 : Public Infrastructure with respect to South Asia

Table 4. Public Infrastructure

S No	Country	Quality Communication and Transport Infrastructure		
		Global Competitiveness Report 2014		
		Year	Index	Score
Pakistan with respect to South Asia				
1	Afghanistan	2013	0.00	0.00
2	Bangladesh	2013	2.80	1.00
3	Bhutan	2013	4.60	1.65
4	India	2013	3.70	1.33
5	Maldives	2013	0.00	0.00
6	Nepal	2013	2.90	1.04
7	Pakistan	2013	3.30	1.18
8	Sri Lanka	2013	5.00	1.79
	Total		22.3	8.00
	Average		2.79	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries				
1	Pakistan	2013	3.30	0.62
2	Australia	2013	5.10	0.95
3	Austria	2013	6.20	1.16
4	Belgium	2013	5.80	1.08
5	Canada	2013	5.60	1.05
6	Chile	2013	4.70	0.88
7	Czech Republic	2013	5.00	0.93
8	Denmark	2013	5.80	1.08
9	Estonia	2013	5.20	0.97
10	Finland	2013	6.40	1.20
11	France	2013	6.10	1.14
12	Germany	2013	6.00	1.12
13	Greece	2013	4.60	0.86
14	Hungary	2013	5.00	0.93
15	Iceland	2013	6.20	1.16
16	Ireland	2013	5.10	0.95
17	Israel	2013	4.40	0.82
18	Italy	2013	4.60	0.86
19	Japan	2013	6.20	1.16
20	South Korea	2013	5.50	1.03
21	Luxembourg	2013	5.90	1.10
22	Mexico	2013	4.20	0.78
23	Netherlands	2013	6.30	1.18

24	New Zealand	2013	5.10	0.95
25	Norway	2013	5.30	0.99
26	Poland	2013	4.00	0.75
27	Portugal	2013	6.00	1.12
28	Slovakia	2013	4.20	0.78
29	Slovenia	2013	5.10	0.95
30	Spain	2013	5.90	1.10
31	Sweden	2013	5.70	1.07
32	Switzerland	2013	6.60	1.23
33	Turkey	2013	5.10	0.95
34	United Kingdom	2013	5.30	0.99
35	United States	2013	5.80	1.08
	Total		187.30	35.00
	Average		5.35	1.00

When compared with 34 OECD countries (Figure 9), Pakistan is lowest with a score of 0.62 while Switzerland leads with as score of 1.23.

Distribution

The graph (Figure 10) shows comparison of distribution of wealth determined by the Gini index. The data analysis is tabulated in table 5. In South Asia, Pakistan has a score of 1.09 after Afghanistan which leads with a score of 1.12. Sri Lanka is the lowest with a score of 0.79.

Table 5. Distribution

S No	Country	Inequality of Income Distribution GINI Index			
		CIA World factbook and UNDP Report			
		Year	0-100	Inequality Control	Score
Pakistan with respect to South Asia					
1	Afghanistan	2013	27.8	72.2	1.12
2	Bangladesh	2010	32.1	67.9	1.05
3	Bhutan	2012	38.7	61.3	0.95
4	India	2004	36.8	63.2	0.98
5	Maldives	2004	37.4	62.6	0.97
6	Nepal	2010	32.8	67.2	1.04
7	Pakistan	2011	29.6	70.4	1.09
8	Sri Lanka	2010	49	51	0.79
	Total		284.2	515.8	8
	Average		35.53	64.48	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries					
1	Pakistan	2011	29.60	70.40	1.03
2	Australia	2008	30.30	69.70	1.02

3	Austria		26.30	73.70	1.08
4	Belgium		25.90	74.10	1.08
5	Canada		32.10	67.90	0.99
6	Chile		52.10	47.90	0.70
7	Czech Republic		24.90	75.10	1.10
8	Denmark		24.80	75.20	1.10
9	Estonia		31.30	68.70	1.00
10	Finland		26.80	73.20	1.07
11	France		30.90	69.10	1.01
12	Germany		27.00	73.00	1.07
13	Greece		34.40	65.60	0.96
14	Hungary		24.70	75.30	1.10
15	Iceland		28.00	72.00	1.05
16	Ireland		33.90	66.10	0.97
17	Israel		37.60	62.40	0.91
18	Italy		31.90	68.10	1.00
19	Japan		37.60	62.40	0.91
20	South Korea		31.10	68.90	1.01
21	Luxembourg		30.40	69.60	1.02
22	Mexico		48.30	51.70	0.76
23	Netherlands		25.10	74.90	1.10
24	New Zealand		36.20	63.80	0.93
25	Norway		25.00	75.00	1.10
26	Poland		34.10	65.90	0.96
27	Portugal		34.20	65.80	0.96
28	Slovakia		26.00	74.00	1.08
29	Slovenia		23.70	76.30	1.12
30	Spain		34.00	66.00	0.97
31	Sweden		23.00	77.00	1.13
32	Switzerland		28.70	71.30	1.04
33	Turkey		40.20	59.80	0.87
34	United Kingdom		32.30	67.70	0.99
35	United States		45.00	55.00	0.80
	Total		1107.40	2392.60	35.00
	Average		31.64	68.36	1.00

As regards to comparison with 34 OECD countries (Figure 11), Pakistan ranks fifteenth with a score of 1.03 while United States, Mexico and Chile being the lowest three with a score of 0.8, 0.76 and 0.70 respectively. Sweden leads with a score of 1.13.

Figure 11 : Distribution with respect to OECD Countries

Stability

In terms of stability, Pakistan achieves a score of 1.12 and stands third in South Asia with Maldives having least inflation rate being the top scorer with a score of 2.59. The graph (Figure 12) shows comparison of stability indicator. The data analysis is tabulated in table 6 given on the next page.

Figure 12 :Stability with respect to South Asia

Table 6. Stability

S N o	Country	Stability of GDP Growth		Inflation				Average Score
				Global Competitiveness Report 2014 and CIA World fact Book				
		Year	Score	Year	%	Inflation Control	Score	
Pakistan with respect to South Asia								
1	Afghanistan			2013	7.60	2.40	1.04	
2	Bangladesh			2013	7.50	2.50	1.08	
3	Bhutan			2013	8.70	1.30	0.56	
4	India			2013	9.50	0.50	0.22	
5	Maldives			2013	4.00	6.00	2.59	
6	Nepal			2013	9.90	0.10	0.04	
7	Pakistan			2013	7.40	2.60	1.12	
8	Sri Lanka			2013	6.90	3.10	1.34	
	Total	0			61.5	18.5	8.00	
	Average	0.00			7.69	2.31	1.00	
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries								
1	Pakistan			2013	7.40	2.60	0.32	
2	Australia			2013	2.50	7.50	0.92	
3	Austria			2013	2.10	7.90	0.97	
4	Belgium			2013	1.20	8.80	1.08	
5	Canada			2013	1.00	9.00	1.10	
6	Chile			2013	1.80	8.20	1.01	
7	Czech Republic			2013	1.40	8.60	1.06	
8	Denmark			2013	0.80	9.20	1.13	
9	Estonia			2013	3.50	6.50	0.80	
10	Finland			2013	2.20	7.80	0.96	
11	France			2013	1.00	9.00	1.10	
12	Germany			2013	1.60	8.40	1.03	
13	Greece			2013	-0.90	10.90	1.34	
14	Hungary			2013	1.70	8.30	1.02	
15	Iceland			2013	3.90	6.10	0.75	
16	Ireland			2013	0.50	9.50	1.17	
17	Israel			2013	1.50	8.50	1.04	
18	Italy			2013	1.30	8.70	1.07	
19	Japan			2013	0.40	9.60	1.18	
20	South Korea			2013	1.30	8.70	1.07	
21	Luxembourg			2013	1.70	8.30	1.02	
22	Mexico			2013	3.80	6.20	0.76	

23	Netherlands			2013	2.60	7.40	0.91	
24	New Zealand			2013	1.10	8.90	1.09	
25	Norway			2013	2.10	7.90	0.97	
26	Poland			2013	0.90	9.10	1.12	
27	Portugal			2013	0.40	9.60	1.18	
28	Slovakia			2013	1.50	8.50	1.04	
29	Slovenia			2013	1.60	8.40	1.03	
30	Spain			2013	1.50	8.50	1.04	
31	Sweden			2013	0.00	10.00	1.23	
32	Switzerland			2013	-0.20	10.20	1.25	
33	Turkey			2013	7.50	2.50	0.31	
34	United Kingdom			2013	2.60	7.40	0.91	
35	United States			2013	1.50	8.50	1.04	
	Total	0.00			64.80	285.20	35.00	
	Average	0.00			1.85	8.15	1.00	

Pakistan stands lowest with a score of 0.32 followed by Turkey with a score of 0.31 when compared with 34 OECD countries (Figure 13). Greece having a negative inflation rate along with Switzerland tops the position with a score of 1.34 followed by Switzerland with a score of 1.25.

Figure 13 : Stability with respect to OECD Countries

Economic Performance

Pakistan stands fifth in Economic performance in South Asia with a score of 0.84. Maldives is at the top with a score of 1.97 due to highest GDP in South Asia despite having highest unemployment rate in South Asia. Sri Lanka although second with a score of 1.25 has the highest growth rate and second highest GDP in South Asia. The graph (Figure 14) shows comparison of Economic Performance indicator. The data analysis is tabulated in table 7 given on next page.

Out of 34 OECD countries, Luxembourg tops the charts with a score of 1.9. Pakistan stands fourth with a score of 1.73. Greece has the lowest score of -0.54. The graph (Figure 15) shows comparison of Economic Performance indicator of 34 OECD countries.

Table 7. Economic Performance

S	Country	GDP Per Capita (PPP)			GDP Growth			Unemployment for last 10 Years				Average Score
		Global Competitiveness Report 2014			World Bank			World Economic Outlook Oct, 2013 and CIA World Factbook				
		Year	US Dollars	Score	Year	%	Score	Year	Un-employment	Employment	Score	
Pakistan with respect to South Asia												
1	Afghanistan	2014	2000	0.65	2013	1.9	0.42	2008	35	65	0.77	0.61
2	Bangladesh	2013	904	0.29	2013	6	1.33	2014	5	95	1.12	0.92
3	Bhutan	2013	2665	0.87	2013	2	0.44	Av 2004-14	3.25	96.75	1.14	0.82
4	India	2013	1505	0.49	2013	6.9	1.53	2014	8.6	91.4	1.08	1.03
5	Maldives	2014	12400	4.03	2013	3.7	0.82	2012	11	89	1.05	1.97
6	Nepal	2013	693	0.23	2013	3.8	0.84	2008	46	54	0.64	0.57
7	Pakistan	2013	1308	0.42	2013	4.4	0.98	Av 2004-14	6.29	93.71	1.10	0.84
8	Sri Lanka	2013	3162	1.03	2013	7.3	1.62	Av 2004-14	5.62	94.38	1.11	1.25
	Total		24637	8		36	8		120.76	679.24	8.00	8.00
	Average		3079.63	1.00		4.50	1.00		15.10	84.91	1.00	1.00
Pakistan with respect to OECD Countries												
1	Pakistan	2013	1308	0.03	2013	4.4	4.13	Av 2004-14	6.29	93.71	1.01	1.73
2	Australia	2013	64863	1.65	2013	2.5	2.35	Av 2004-14	5.15	94.85	1.03	1.67
3	Austria	2013	48957	1.24	2013	0.2	0.19	Av 2004-14	4.59	95.41	1.03	0.82
4	Belgium	2013	45384	1.15	2013	0.3	0.28	Av 2004-14	7.97	92.03	1.00	0.81
5	Canada	2013	51990	1.32	2013	2	1.88	Av 2004-14	7.06	92.94	1.01	1.40

6	Chile	2013	15776	0.40	2013	4.1	3.85	Av 2004-14	7.92	92.08	1.00	1.75
7	Czech Republic	2013	18858	0.48	2013	-0.7	-0.66	Av 2004-14	6.88	93.12	1.01	0.28
8	Denmark	2013	59191	1.50	2013	-0.5	-0.47	Av 2004-14	5.85	94.15	1.02	0.68
9	Estonia	2013	19032	0.48	2013	1.6	1.50	Av 2004-14	9.29	90.71	0.98	0.99
10	Finland	2013	47129	1.20	2013	-1.2	-1.13	Av 2004-14	7.84	92.16	1.00	0.36
11	France	2013	43000	1.09	2013	0.3	0.28	Av 2004-14	9.56	90.44	0.98	0.78
12	Germany	2013	44999	1.14	2013	0.1	0.09	Av 2004-14	7.78	92.22	1.00	0.75
13	Greece	2013	21857	0.56	2013	-3.3	-3.10	Av 2004-14	14.73	85.27	0.92	-0.54
14	Hungary	2013	13405	0.34	2013	1.5	1.41	Av 2004-14	9.32	90.68	0.98	0.91
15	Iceland	2013	45356	1.15	2013	3.5	3.28	Av 2004-14	4.37	95.63	1.04	1.82
16	Ireland	2013	45621	1.16	2013	0.2	0.19	Av 2004-14	9.7	90.3	0.98	0.77
17	Israel	2013	37035	0.94	2013	3.2	3.00	Av 2004-14	8.78	91.22	0.99	1.64
18	Italy	2013	34715	0.88	2013	-1.9	-1.78	Av 2004-14	8.69	91.31	0.99	0.03
19	Japan	2013	38491	0.98	2013	1.6	1.50	Av 2004-14	4.42	95.58	1.04	1.17
20	South Korea	2013	24329	0.62	2013	3	2.82	Av 2004-14	3.43	96.57	1.05	1.49
21	Luxembour g	2013	110424	2.81	2013	2	1.88	Av 2004-14	5.17	94.83	1.03	1.90

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22	Mexico	2013	10630	0.27	2013	1.1	1.03	Av 2004-14	4.46	95.54	1.03	0.78
23	Netherlands	2013	47634	1.21	2013	-0.7	-0.66	Av 2004-14	4.9	95.1	1.03	0.53
24	New Zealand	2013	40481	1.03	2013	2.5	2.35	Av 2004-14	5.17	94.83	1.03	1.47
25	Norway	2013	100318	2.55	2013	0.6	0.56	Av 2004-14	3.41	96.59	1.05	1.39
26	Poland	2013	13394	0.34	2013	1.7	1.60	Av 2004-14	11.52	88.48	0.96	0.96
27	Portugal	2013	20728	0.53	2013	-1.4	-1.31	Av 2004-14	11.03	88.97	0.96	0.06
28	Slovakia	2013	17706	0.45	2013	1.4	1.31	Av 2004-14	13.82	86.18	0.93	0.90
29	Slovenia	2013	22756	0.58	2013	-1	-0.94	Av 2004-14	7.23	92.77	1.00	0.21
30	Spain	2013	29150	0.74	2013	-1.2	-1.13	Av 2004-14	16.95	83.05	0.90	0.17
31	Sweden	2013	57909	1.47	2013	1.5	1.41	Av 2004-14	7.52	92.48	1.00	1.29
32	Switzerland	2013	81324	2.07	2013	1.9	1.78	Av 2004-14	3.25	96.75	1.05	1.63
33	Turkey	2013	10815	0.27	2013	4.1	3.85	Av 2004-14	10.55	89.45	0.97	1.70
34	United Kingdom	2013	39567	1.01	2013	1.7	1.60	Av 2004-14	6.6	93.4	1.01	1.20
35	United States	2013	53101	1.35	2013	2.2	2.06	Av 2004-14	6.96	93.04	1.01	1.47
	Total		137723 3.00	35.00		37.3 0	35.00		268.16	3231.84	35.00	35.00
	Average		39349.5	1.00		1.07	1.00		7.66	92.34	1.00	1.00

Public Sector Performance (PSP) Index

After combining the score of the individual indicators, the Public Sector Performance (PSP) Index and ranking of the countries is calculated as tabulated in Table 8.

Table 8. Public Sector Performance (PSP) Indicators

S. No.	Country	Opportunity Indicators				Musgravian Indicators			PSP Index	Rank
		Administrative	Education	Health	Public Infrastructure	Distribution	Stability	Economic Performance		
Pakistan with Respect to South Asian Countries										
1	Sri Lanka	1.34	1.79	1.07	1.79	0.79	1.34	1.25	1.34	1
2	Bhutan	1.47	1.43	1.01	1.65	0.95	0.56	0.82	1.13	2
3	Maldives	0.81	0.00	1.07	0.00	0.97	2.59	1.97	1.06	3
4	Pakistan	1.08	0.96	0.98	1.18	1.09	1.12	0.84	1.04	4
5	India	1.20	1.41	0.99	1.33	0.98	0.22	1.03	1.02	5
6	Bangladesh	0.84	1.11	1.03	1.00	1.05	1.08	0.92	1.00	6
7	Nepal	1.11	1.29	1.01	1.04	1.04	0.04	0.57	0.87	7
8	Afghanistan	0.16	0.00	0.84	0.00	1.12	1.04	0.61	0.54	8
	Total	1.34	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00	0.54	
	Average	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.07	
Pakistan with Respect to OECD Countries										
1	Switzerland	1.19	1.16	1.02	1.23	1.04	1.25	1.63	1.22	1
2	Luxembourg	1.10	1.02	1.01	1.10	1.02	1.02	1.90	1.17	2
3	Iceland	1.11	1.09	1.02	1.16	1.05	0.75	1.82	1.14	3
4	Australia	1.12	1.21	1.01	0.95	1.02	0.92	1.67	1.13	4
5	Sweden	1.16	1.01	1.01	1.07	1.13	1.23	1.29	1.13	5
6	New Zealand	1.24	1.19	1.01	0.95	0.93	1.09	1.47	1.13	6
7	Canada	1.15	1.10	1.01	1.05	0.99	1.10	1.40	1.11	7
8	Norway	1.18	1.12	1.01	0.99	1.10	0.97	1.39	1.11	8
9	Japan	1.11	1.00	1.02	1.16	0.91	1.18	1.17	1.08	9
10	United States	1.12	0.99	0.99	1.08	0.80	1.04	1.47	1.07	10
11	South Korea	0.92	0.89	1.01	1.03	1.01	1.07	1.49	1.06	11
12	Denmark	1.17	1.16	1.00	1.08	1.10	1.13	0.68	1.05	12
13	Israel	0.94	0.92	1.01	0.82	0.91	1.04	1.64	1.04	13

14	United Kingdom	1.17	0.99	1.01	0.99	0.99	0.91	1.20	1.04	14
15	Germany	1.14	1.09	1.01	1.12	1.07	1.03	0.75	1.03	15
16	Chile	1.01	0.86	1.00	0.88	0.70	1.01	1.75	1.03	16
17	Belgium	1.00	1.13	1.00	1.08	1.08	1.08	0.81	1.03	17
18	Ireland	1.09	1.20	1.01	0.95	0.97	1.17	0.77	1.02	18
19	Austria	1.09	0.99	1.01	1.16	1.08	0.97	0.82	1.02	19
20	France	1.01	1.04	1.02	1.14	1.01	1.10	0.78	1.02	20
21	Netherlands	1.15	1.24	1.01	1.18	1.10	0.91	0.53	1.02	21
22	Finland	1.21	1.20	1.01	1.20	1.07	0.96	0.36	1.00	22
23	Estonia	0.99	1.03	0.98	0.97	1.00	0.80	0.99	0.97	23
24	Hungary	0.84	0.87	0.97	0.93	1.10	1.02	0.91	0.95	24
25	Poland	0.87	0.89	0.98	0.75	0.96	1.12	0.96	0.93	25
26	Turkey	0.81	0.81	0.97	0.95	0.87	0.31	1.70	0.92	26
27	Slovakia	0.82	0.78	0.98	0.78	1.08	1.04	0.90	0.91	27
28	Portugal	0.91	1.04	1.00	1.12	0.96	1.18	0.06	0.90	28
29	Spain	0.90	1.03	1.02	1.10	0.97	1.04	0.17	0.89	29
30	Czech Republic	0.86	0.88	0.99	0.93	1.10	1.06	0.28	0.87	30
31	Slovenia	0.81	0.95	1.00	0.95	1.12	1.03	0.21	0.87	31
32	Pakistan	0.60	0.57	0.88	0.62	1.03	0.32	1.73	0.82	32
33	Italy	0.71	0.92	1.02	0.86	1.00	1.07	0.03	0.80	33
34	Mexico	0.77	0.74	0.98	0.78	0.76	0.76	0.78	0.80	34
35	Greece	0.74	0.87	1.01	0.86	0.96	1.34	-0.54	0.75	35
Total		35.0								
Average		1								

Conclusion

The Public Sector Performance (PSP) Index provides empirical evidence of difference between countries. Pakistan ranks 4th among the 8 countries of South Asia while it is 32nd when compared with 34 OECD countries of the world. In South Asia, Pakistan's performance is 4 % above the normalized weighted average while it is 18 % below the normalized weighted average when compared with 34 OECD countries.

Recommendations

As a result of the above mentioned study, it is recommended that important related coefficient (α) which has been taken as 1, be calculated for each indicator. Moreover, Public expenditure relevant to the category be utilized for weighing performance to indicate the Public Sector Efficiency.

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